

ANOMALY DETECTION FOR THE MONITORING SERVICE

September 2022

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

Monitoring has proved to be a crucial part of the operation lifecycle of any computer system, as it provides access to important internal information about the behavior and state of the system at a given point in time. With the evolution of the systems more complex monitoring cases emerged that need an innovative approach, achievable only by involving machine learning and anomaly detection techniques. The IT Monitoring Service at CERN (MONIT) is a central infrastructure collecting data and providing advanced dashboards and alarms for the CERN IT Data Centre and the WLCG infrastructure, and as any other computer system it also requires monitoring of its internal components in order to guarantee normal operation and avoid the potential outages. Aiming at covering the anomaly detection demand, the IT Monitoring in collaboration with other IT Computing teams have been working on a project (ADMON) meant to simplify the development and production deployment of AD models. The major goal of this project is identifying and creating an anomaly detection model for monitoring use cases within the MONIT infrastructure that cannot be easily covered by the traditional threshold-based alerting methods. It will also make use of the ADMON infrastructure in order to simplify the process and prove its efficiency.

ABSTRACT

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This project will focus on developing an anomaly detection model for improving the MONIT internal monitoring by using the ADMON infrastructure. An interesting use case has been identified with a documents producer agent that is pulling data from external data sources. The misbehavior of the agent is difficult to be monitored with the traditional threshold-based alerts as very often problems are caused by changes in the data rates or partially missing data. The project provides few challenges as it is based on non-annotated time series data that will require feature engineering decisions making and developing model evaluation functionality. The process of developing the anomaly detection model will cover standard steps as studying, observing the historical data, and future engineering, while using the ADMON API for data acquisition and initial aggregation. Different models will be trained and evaluated using various unsupervised learning algorithms. The best-performing model will be chosen for production deployment in the ADMON infrastructure and will serve as an essential tool in the daily work of the MONIT service managers.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

.....

1	INTRODUCTION	4
1.1	Anomaly Detection	4
1.2	ADMON	5
1.3	ADMON API	6
1.4	Detection Process	6
2	OUTLIER DETECTION WITH UNSUPERVISED LEARNING	7
2.1	Data	7
2.2	Isolation Forest	9
2.2.1	Accuracy Measures	15
2.2.2	Accuracy Measures for Isolation Forest	16
2.3	Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise	17
2.3.1	Accuracy Measures for DBSCAN	21
3	CONCLUSION	22
4	ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	22
5	REFERENCES	23

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Anomaly Detection

Anomaly detection also known as outlier detection is the process of finding data points within a dataset that differs from the rest. Common applications of anomaly detection includes fraud detection in financial transactions, fault detection and predictive maintenance, and networking. There are various ways of performing anomaly detection and the approach you take will depend on the nature of the data and the types of anomalies you are looking for. In general, there are three approaches for identifying observations that may be considered anomalous given a sample’s distribution:

1. Supervised
2. Semi-Supervised
3. Unsupervised

Figure 1: [The Anomaly Detection approaches]

Supervised anomaly detection requires a labeled dataset that indicates if a record is “normal” or “abnormal”. Unsupervised anomaly detection methods assume that the time-series data is unlabeled. In this paper, we will focus on unsupervised anomaly detection methods and use unlabeled datasets in our experiments to evaluate them.

Large datasets may have very complicated patterns that are difficult to detect by just looking at the data. That’s why the study of anomaly detection is an extremely important application of Machine Learning. It is an important data mining tool for discovering induced errors, unexpected patterns, and more generally anomalies.

Anomaly detection can help identify issues before they become a problem and can help to optimize processes by identifying patterns that we may not have been aware of.

In this work applies Isolation Forest and Clustering methods.

1.2 ADMON

ADMON is a project meant to provide infrastructure focused on simplifying the development and operation of Anomaly Detection monitoring processes for data stored in the MONIT infrastructure. It provides a set of APIs and components which integrates with CERN ML Service (Kubeflow) and automates the generation and delivery of prediction results to MONIT.

The main focus of the project is simplifying the work of the CERN Service Managers and other MONIT users in their effort to configure and run continuously Anomaly Detection monitoring processes. The current solution to spot anomalous servers relies on a threshold-based alarming system carefully set by the system managers on the performance metrics of each infrastructure’s component. In most cases, such monitoring is based on Machine Learning models and ADMON is designed around that approach.

In general, the process of developing AD model and metrics could be split in a few steps:

1. studying and observing historical data;
2. developing and training the model;
3. deploying the model in production;
4. inferencing the model with fresh data and storing the prediction results;

Taking the above steps into consideration and the fact the CERN ML Service (Kubeflow) provides infrastructure for developing, training, and deploying models in production, it has been considered that ADMON could provide the required integration between the services and add extra value by:

- unified data access API
- automated model inference process and prediction delivery to MONIT
- catalog of existing models and their repositories/configurations

Architecture:

The ADMON architecture is described in the following diagram:

Figure 2: [Architecture of the ADMON project]

1.3 ADMON API

ADMON API is the interface used by the users to interact with ADMON. It is serving the following purposes:

- registers the users' AD projects into the system with the corresponding metadata's config;
- provides easy access to historical MONIT data (stored in HDFS) for observation and training purposes;

Figure 3: [Architecture of the ADMON API]

Functionality:

Internally the API will perform the following operations corresponding to the steps:

1. Register the project into the ADMON Metadata Service.
2. Store the latest configuration locally and build the path(s) for the required dataset. Construct and return the pre-built dataset to the user (e.g. Spark, Pandas).
3. Register the additional configuration data into the Metadata Service.

1.4 Detection Process

The ADMON Detection Process is the component responsible for inferencing the model with fresh data and transforming the predictions into valid MONIT documents.

The complete process is done in a few steps and triggered based on the configuration metadata registered and stored within the Metadata Service.

Figure 4: [Architecture of the Detection Process]

Functionality:

ADMON Detection Process is meant to be a fully automated and configuration-driven process. It checks periodically the configuration stored in the Metadata Service and starts processing once it identifies that prediction is required.

It executes the following steps:

1. Consumes the required data from MONIT Kafka
2. Does basic simple transformation (if such is configured) and perform HTTP request to the corresponding Inference Server
3. Converts the obtained result into MONIT document(s)
4. Sends the converted documents to the MONIT infrastructure

2 OUTLIER DETECTION WITH UNSUPERVISED LEARNING

We have "reference" training data at hand but unfortunately without knowing which rows are outliers or not. Here, it is tempting to let statistical algorithms do the guess work. This paper will be the observation of some typical approaches:

- density based: Isolation Forest algorithm
- distance-based: DBSCAN algorithm. It groups together points that are close to each other based on a distance measurement

In this paper is used unlabeled dataset and it assumes that the majority data points in the unlabeled dataset are “normal” and it looks for data points that differs from the “normal” data points.

2.1 Data

In this detecting process uses 11 metrics. It is Kafka rate metrics for topics from MONIT HTTP Data Source which is pulling data from different endpoints:

- sitemon raw profiles
- snow raw services
- cric raw
- cric raw ddmendpoint
- cric raw extra
- cric raw pandaqueue
- cric raw pledges
- cric raw sitecapacities
- cric raw topology
- monit test raw
- puppetdb raw fact

Exploring the Data:

The machine learning task in this work is the study and construction of algorithms that can learn from and make predictions on data. Such algorithms function by making data-driven predictions or decisions, by building a mathematical model from input data. These input data used to build the model will be divided into multiple data sets.

Three data sets are used in different stages of the creation of the model: training, validation, and testing sets.

Figure 5: [Training Resampled Dataset]

The original dataset has a data period of 1 hour. Data were resampled into longer intervals as some data is received only once every 12 hours.

The model is initially fit on a training data set, which is a set of examples used to fit the parameters of the model.

timestamp	value_crsi	value_crpl	value_crt	value_prf	value_crp	value_mrt	value_srp	value_crd	value_cr	value_srs	value_cre
2022-01-01 00:00:00	0.000342	0.000337	0.002469	0.007148	0.011010	0.166684	0.000000	0.004737	0.000330	0.000562	0.002008
2022-01-01 12:00:00	0.000628	0.000619	0.004528	0.014072	0.011714	0.166661	0.000013	0.004913	0.000334	0.000602	0.001957
2022-01-02 00:00:00	0.000664	0.000651	0.004766	0.014069	0.011313	0.166688	0.000014	0.004956	0.000334	0.000609	0.001976
2022-01-02 12:00:00	0.000628	0.000618	0.004527	0.015473	0.011796	0.166608	0.000013	0.004953	0.000333	0.000602	0.001972
2022-01-03 00:00:00	0.000628	0.000619	0.004527	0.013447	0.011710	0.166689	0.000013	0.004912	0.000333	0.000602	0.001956

Figure 6: [Training Resampled Dataset]

The validation set is sampled from the training set. The fitted model is used to predict the responses for the observations in a second data set called the validation dataset. Using `train_test_split` from `sklearn.model_selection` split the dataset into 66% training data and 33% validation data.

The test data set is a data set used to provide an unbiased evaluation of a final model fit on the training data set.

Plot a few topics from resampled dataset to see how data looks using `plotly.express`:

Figure 7: [monit_test_raw data]

Figure 8: [cric_raw_pandaqueue data]

Figure 9: [monit_test_raw data]

Figure 10: [cric_raw_sitecapacities data]

2.2 Isolation Forest

Isolation Forests (IF) build based on the Decision Tree algorithm. It isolates the outliers by randomly selecting a feature from the given set of features and then randomly selecting a split value between the max and min values of that feature.

IF were built based on the fact that anomalies are the data points that are “few and different”. And since there are no pre-defined labels here, it is an unsupervised model.

1. When given a dataset, a random sub-sample of the data is selected and assigned to a binary tree.
2. Branching of the tree starts by selecting a random feature (from the set of all N features) first. And then branching is done on a random threshold (any value in the range of minimum and maximum values of the selected feature).
3. If the value of a data point is less than the selected threshold, it goes to the left branch else to the right. And thus a node is split into left and right branches.
4. This process from step 2 is continued recursively till each data point is completely isolated or till max depth(if defined) is reached.
5. The above steps are repeated to construct random binary trees.
 - (a) a normal point x_l requires twelve random partitions to be isolated;
 - (b) an anomaly x_o requires only four partitions to be isolated.
 - (c) averaged path lengths of x_l and x_o convergewhen the number of trees increases.

Anomalies are more susceptible to isolation and hence have short path lengths. An example below of isolating an inlier X_i and an outlier X_o . The anomalous point X_o can be isolated with significantly fewer partitions than X_i .

(a) Isolating x_i (b) / Isolating x_o

(c) Average path lengths converge

[Figure 11.]

Because of their susceptibility to isolation, anomalies are isolated closer to the root of the tree; where abnormal points are isolated at the deeper end of the tree. This isolation characteristic of the tree forms the basis of our method to detect anomalies, and we call this tree Isolation Tree or iTree. Isolation Forest builds an ensemble of iTrees for a given data set, then anomalies are those instances that have short average pathlengths on the iTrees. There are only two variables in this method: the number of trees to build and the sub-samplingsize.

Training Isolation Forest model:

The algorithm starts with the training of the data, by generating Isolation Trees. The training data is used to train the model.

During training time, IF follows the following steps:

1. Take a subsample X from the dataset, with $|X| = n$;

2. Construct an iTree by randomly partitioning this sub-sampled dataset X with binary splits. An iTree is built by recursively selecting a random feature of your data and a random value to split the data in two branches. This process stops when either a predefined maximum height of the tree is reached or when the dataset cannot be split further because it contains only one element $|X_{\iota}| = 1$ at level ι .

Repeat this multiple times and create a predefined number of iTrees. After an ensemble of iTrees is created, model training is complete.

At test time:

1. Pass each test instance to an iTree and starting from the root of the tree and the attributes of the instance follow the path according to the nodes' splits. Once it reaches a leaf, record the height (called path length);
2. Repeat this for every iTree in the ensemble;
3. Compute the average of the path length for that test instance;
4. Convert this into an Anomaly Score using the following formula:

$$SIF(x, n) = 2^{-\left(\frac{E(h(x))}{c(n)}\right)}$$

where:

- x is the test instance.
- $E(h(x))$ is the average value of path length in an ensemble of tree.

$$c(n) = 2 * H(n - 1) - \left(\frac{2 * (n - 1)}{n}\right)$$

where n is the number of instances in dataset X and H is the Harmonic Number approximated via the following equation $H(\iota) = \ln(\iota) + \gamma$ (Euler's constant = 0.577215).

Detected anomalies on training data:

In the Figure 14 is the visualization of the distribution of the predictions:

Figure 14: [Distribution of the predictions]

Figure 15: [monit_test_raw data]

Figure 16: [cric_raw_pandaqueuet data]

Figure 17: [puppetdb_raw_fact]

Figure 18: [cric_raw_sitecapacities data]

This is a sample of the data held during model training, needed to evaluate the skills of the model when tuning the hyperparameters of the model.

All the predictions are either 1 or -1. Where 1 shows the data point is normal while -1 represents the outliers.

In the Figures 15-18 are plots of the outliers based on the training dataset using a different color on the same scattered plots as were shown earlier in the "Exploring the Data" part.

Figures 19-22 are the same plots of the outliers but based on the validation dataset. We can see less outliers here because the validation dataset is only 33% of the whole data as was said before.

Detected anomalies on validation data:

Figure 19: [monit_test_raw data]

Figure 20: [puppetdb_raw_fact data]

Figure 21: [cric_raw_pandaqueuet data] Figure 22: [cric_raw_sitecapacities data]

Calculates the anomaly score based on the mean/standard deviation method. The empirical rule.

When the data, or certain features in the dataset, follow a normal distribution, we can use the standard deviation of the data to detect outliers.

In statistics, standard deviation measures the spread of data around the mean, and in essence, it captures how far away from the mean the data points are.

The empirical rule also referred to as the three-sigma rule or 68-95-99.7 rule, is a statistical rule that states that for a normal distribution, almost all observed data will fall within three standard deviations, denoted by σ of the mean or average denoted by μ .

Figure 23: [3 Standard Deviation Method]

In particular, the empirical rule predicts that 68 % of observations falls within the first standard deviation ($\mu \pm \sigma$), 95% within the first two standard deviations ($\mu \pm 2\sigma$), and 99.7% within the first three standard deviations ($\mu \pm 3\sigma$).

One approach to outlier detection is to set the lower limit to three standard deviations below the mean ($\mu - 3 * \sigma$), and the upper limit to three standard deviations above the mean ($\mu + 3 * \sigma$). Any data point that falls outside this range is detected as an outlier.

Creating a function `find_anomalies_timewindow` will set upper and lower limits to 3 standard deviations. Here is applying this function for each attribute in the validation dataset.

Implementation of applying the function, which set the upper and lower limits to 3 standard deviations shown in Figure 21:


```

timestamp
2022-04-16 12:00:00    0.000947
2022-04-15 00:00:00    0.000946
2022-01-04 00:00:00    0.000628
2022-04-10 00:00:00    0.000947
2022-04-20 00:00:00    0.000909
...
2022-04-11 00:00:00    0.000946
2022-03-08 12:00:00    0.000946
2022-01-26 12:00:00    0.000676
2022-03-27 12:00:00    0.000946
2022-03-01 12:00:00    0.000960
Name: value_crsi, Length: 100, dtype: float64
0.00019036144408727255
0.00037990126963313633
0.0011413470459822265
    
```

Figure 24: [Metric cric_raw_sitecapacities]

Generate outliers:

Based on the above validation score we can generate outliers for each value in the validation dataset. During scoring, a data point is traversed through all the trees which were trained earlier. Then, an ‘anomaly score’ is assigned to each of the data points based on the depth of the tree required to arrive at that point. This score is an aggregation of the depth obtained from each of the iTrees. An anomaly score of -1 is assigned to anomalies and 1 to normal points based on the contamination(percentage of anomalies present in the data) parameter provided.

In Figure 25 shows the output for generated outliers based on the anomaly score :

anomalies_cric	anomalies_prf	anomalies_crp	anomalies_mrt	anomalies_srp	anomalies_crd	anomalies_cr	anomalies_srs	anomalies_cre	anomaly_score
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	1	1	1	-1	1	1	1	1	-1
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Figure 25: [Anomaly score in validation dataset]

Average Precision Score

Compute average precision (AP), from validation prediction scores using sklearn.metrics.

AP summarizes a precision-recall curve as the weighted mean of precisions achieved at each threshold, with the increase in recall from the previous threshold used as the weight:

$$AP = \sum_n (R_n - R_{n-1})P_n$$

Figure 26: [Average Precision Score Formula]

-where P_n and R_n are the precision and recall at the nth threshold.

This implementation is not interpolated and is different from computing the area under the precision-recall curve with the trapezoidal rule, which uses linear interpolation and can be too optimistic.

The output of the average precision score based on the prediction of the validation dataset and anomaly score:

0.9888714053174172

Figure 27: [Average Precision Score]

We used the average precision score metric to measure the results obtained.

2.2.1 Accuracy Measures

AUROC: Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic

The AUROC indicates whether your model can correctly rank examples. The AUROC is the probability that a randomly selected positive example has a higher predicted probability of being positive than a randomly selected negative example.

The AUROC is calculated as the area underneath a curve that measures the trade-off between the true positive rate (TPR) and false positive rate (FPR) at different decision thresholds. It is defined by FPR and TPR as x and y axes.

$$\text{TPR} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}}, \quad \text{FPR} = \frac{\text{FP}}{\text{FP} + \text{TN}}$$

Figure 28: [TPR and FPR formulas]

A random classifier (e.g. a coin toss) has an AUROC of 0.5, while a perfect classifier has an AUROC of 1.0.

Figure 29: [AUROC]

Average Precision (AUPRC): Area Under the Precision-Recall Curve

Average precision indicates whether the model can correctly identify all the positive examples without accidentally marking too many negative ones as positive. Thus, average precision is high when your model can correctly handle positives. Average precision is calculated as the

area under a curve that measures the trade-off between precision and recall at different decision thresholds.

A random classifier (e.g. a coin toss) has an average precision equal to the percentage of positives in the class, e.g. 0.12 if there are 12% positive examples in the class. A perfect classifier has an average precision of 1.0.

2.2.2 Accuracy Measures for Isolation Forest

The visualization performance of the model we made plots the AUPRC and the AUROC for the anomaly detection model in the latent space:

Figure 30 shows output based on a prediction of the validation dataset and anomaly score:

Figure 30: [AUPRC and AUROC results]

In the output, we have a perfect classifier with an average precision of 1.0. AUROC shows 0.98, which produces a lot of true positives and true negatives. AUROC and average precision are both high, so this is a very good model.

2.3 Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise

The DBSCAN (Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise) is a density-based clustering algorithm. The main principle of this algorithm is that it finds core samples in a dense area and groups the samples around those core samples to create clusters. The samples in a low-density area become outliers.

The Scikit-learn API provides the DBSCAN class for this algorithm. It groups ‘densely grouped’ data points into a single cluster. It can identify clusters in large spatial datasets by looking at the local density of the data points. The most exciting feature of DBSCAN clustering is that it is robust to outliers. It also does not require the number of clusters to be told beforehand.

DBSCAN requires only two parameters: epsilon and minPoints.

Epsilon:

It is a measure of the neighborhood. Epsilon (eps or ϵ) is the radius of the circle to be created around each data point to check the density and minPoints (minPts) is the minimum number of data points required inside that circle for that data point to be classified as a Core point.

minPoints:

minPoints (minPts) is a threshold on the least number of points that we want to see in a point’s neighborhood. In higher dimensions the circle becomes hypersphere, epsilon becomes the radius of that hypersphere, and minPoints is the minimum number of data points required inside that hypersphere.

For example, we have some data points and they represent in grey color:

Figure 31: [Example of data]

DBSCAN creates a circle of epsilon radius around every data point and classifies them into Core point, Border point, and Noise, as it shown in Figure 32.

Figure 32: [Example of how DBSCAN works with some data]

A data point is a Core point if the circle around it contains at least ‘minPoints’ number of points. If the number of points is less than minPoints, then it is classified as Border Point, and if there are no other data points around any data point within an epsilon radius, then it is treated as Noise.

Suppose we are taking minPoints = 3:

Figure 33: [DBSCAN Architecture]

If we have 4 points in our neighborhood, this will also satisfy our threshold minPoints = 3. Because this threshold represents the minimum number of samples in a neighborhood.

Classification of data points:

- Core points

In the above-mentioned figure A is a core point.

A core point must satisfy one condition - the number of neighbors must be greater than or equal to threshold minPoints. If minPoints = 3, then this point satisfies this condition.

- Boundary points

A boundary point has to satisfy two conditions:

- 1) The number of neighbors must be less than minPoints.
- 2) The point should be in the neighborhood of a core point.

In Figure 31 - border point B. The point has less than the number of neighbors in its neighborhood and it is in the neighborhood of another core point. So, this point B is a boundary point or border point.

- Noise points

If a point is neither a core point nor a boundary point, then it is called a noise point.

In the figure 31, point C is neither a core point nor a boundary point. This is a noise point.

- Density edge

Joining by an edge two points in case if they are neighbors.

- Density connected points

Connecting every core point via density edges (p' is in the neighborhood of p'' and similarly for other points. But p and q are not neighbors - two core points are connected via density edges). The first and the last points are density-connected points, as we can see in Figure 34.

Figure 34: [p and q points are density connected]

Preparing the datasets:

This difference in scale of the various metrics is harmful for most anomaly detection algorithms since they will erroneously give weight to the metrics with higher value.

Normalization is used to eliminate redundant data and ensures that good-quality clusters are generated which can improve the efficiency of clustering algorithms. So it becomes an essential step before clustering as Euclidean distance is very sensitive to the changes in the differences.

We need to normalize samples individually to unit norm using `sklearn.preprocessing.Normalizer`. Each sample (i.e. each row of the data matrix) with at least one non-zero component is rescaled independently of other samples so that its norm (l1, l2 or inf) equals one. Scaling inputs to unit norms is a common operation for clustering.

As shown in Figure 30 and Figure 31, the different features have been pre-aligned to the same scale in the datasets.

The output of Normalized datasets:

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	0.541436	0.455804	0.309226	0.104358	0.071392	0.098652	0.097527	0.336758	0.250910	0.409891	0.154489
1	0.540369	0.454904	0.308746	0.103906	0.071653	0.113276	0.097381	0.336807	0.250385	0.409042	0.155069
2	0.538416	0.462876	0.307084	0.102694	0.071041	0.112862	0.096987	0.334064	0.249461	0.407569	0.154511
3	0.537839	0.462473	0.308217	0.102770	0.070516	0.112760	0.096933	0.335283	0.249271	0.407217	0.154369
4	0.535464	0.461694	0.305569	0.103169	0.069421	0.112613	0.096752	0.315219	0.251195	0.428682	0.151688

Figure 35: [Normalized training dataset]

Calculating the anomaly score based on the mean/standard deviation method (this method was discussed in detail in the previous chapter.)

Implementation of applying the function, which set the upper and lower limit to 3 standard deviations shown in the Figure 32:.


```

timestamp
2022-02-02 00:00:00    0.675873
2022-01-24 12:00:00    0.684907
2022-02-04 00:00:00    0.675938
2022-03-22 00:00:00    0.946501
2022-01-29 00:00:00    0.675982
...
2022-01-19 00:00:00    0.627766
2022-04-04 12:00:00    0.946582
2022-01-15 00:00:00    0.627814
2022-04-11 12:00:00    0.946377
2022-05-21 00:00:00    0.655573
Name: value_crsi, Length: 100, dtype: float64
0.17515672854748915
0.38412061706180944
1.084747531251766
    
```

Figure 36: [Anomaly Score for validation dataset]

Based on the above validation score generate outliers for each value in the validation dataset. An anomaly score of -1 is assigned to anomalies and 0 to normal points.

Output for generated outliers based on anomaly score:

anomalies_crt	anomalies_prf	anomalies_crp	anomalies_mrt	anomalies_srp	anomalies_crd	anomalies_cr	anomalies_srs	anomalies_cre	anomaly_score
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1

Figure 37: [Anomaly Score for validation dataset]

Defining the model and anomaly detection:

Define the model by using the DBSCAN class of Scikit-learn API shown in Figure 34. Output has defined the 'eps' and 'min_sample' in the arguments of the class. The argument 'eps' is the distance between two samples to be considered as a neighborhood and 'min_samples' is the number of samples in a neighborhood.

```
DBSCAN(eps=0.1, min_samples=10)
```

Figure 38: [DBSCAN model]

To see how many clusters has it found on the dataset, we can convert this array into a set and we can print the length of the set. Also, by making a prediction based on the normalized datasets we have plots with the prediction results:

Output is 2 clusters. Plots shown in Figures 39-40, where blue points (0) - is normal data, and red points (-1) are anomaly points:

Figure 39: Visualization of 2 clusters in training dataset

Figure 40: Visualization of 2 clusters in validation dataset

2.3.1 Accuracy Measures for DBSCAN

Area Under the Precision-Recall Curve (AUPRC) and Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic (AUROC).

This stage was detailed described in the previous chapter.

In DBSCAN model used the same accuracy measures as in the Isolation Forest model to show the differences in metrics and to compare them.

Output based on a prediction of validation dataset and anomaly score is shown in Figure 41 and Figure 42.

The AUC for this line is 0.93 and ROC shows 0.99 results. In output, we have a good model that produces a lot of true positives and true negatives. We can see that the AUROC and average precision are both high.

Figure 41: AUROC plot

Figure 42: AUPRC plot

3 CONCLUSION

This paper shows how to perform anomaly detection on time series data, and discusses the benefits of anomaly detection and how it helps to explain spikes and dips in the data set.

There were created two anomaly detection models, first using the Isolation Forest algorithm, and second using the Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise algorithm. Prepared datasets were used to build the model. In the course of the study, anomalies in the time series dataset were detected, plotted, and visualised.

Based on the Accuracy Measures of both models, we can conclude which model performs better at finding anomalies in this dataset. We see that the Isolation Forest average precision is 1, while the area under the curve for this algorithm has a score of 0.98. The results are excellent, it was mentioned earlier that the ideal model has a score of 1. Considering the DBSCAN model, the following results were achieved: Average Precision 0.99 and Area under the curve 0.93. This model also gives good results.

Comparing the two models, our evaluation shows that Isolation Forest has higher values, hence produces more true positives and true negatives than DBSCAN, and is better suited for finding anomalies in this dataset.

Essentially, Isolation Forest is an accurate and efficient anomaly detector, especially for large databases. Its capacity in handling high-volume databases is highly desirable for real-life applications.

It has been done using the ADMON and configured for the purpose of the IT Monitoring Service. The most accurate model will be applied to ADMON infrastructure.

4 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

During my nine weeks at CERN, I greatly expanded my knowledge by mastering various technologies, frameworks and platforms that were new to me, as well as deepening and consolidating the knowledge I already knew.

The field of Data Science is an interdisciplinary field, including Computer Science, Statistics, Inference, Machine Learning algorithms, Predictive Analysis, and new technologies.

CERN is a great source for new researches in this field, considering the amount of data being processed every day in the CERN Data Centre. These processes are essential for the development of humanity, as all collected data is meaningless until it is transformed into valuable information.

I would also like to thank my supervisor and my section colleagues for guiding and teaching me throughout my stay and making me feel part of the team. It was a great time and I really could not have been in a better team.

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